

Research on the generating mechanism among research leadership in international cooperation based on GERGM

Ruonan Cai¹, Wencan Tian², Zhigang Hu³

¹*cairuonan123@163.com*, ²*tianwencan@mail.dlut.edu.cn*, ³*huzhigang@dlut.edu.cn*

WISE Lab, Institute of Science of Science and S&T Management, Dalian University of Technology, Dalian (China)

Abstract

This article uses the 235,746 papers published in the field of artificial intelligence from 2001-2020 to quantify dominant scientific relationships based on international collaboration. The analysis of these relationships of international cooperation was systematically explored by referring to both endogenous and exogenous effects. After the generalized exponential random graph model was applied, results were obtained which show that: ① There is a strong tendency for countries to develop mutually-led international scientific collaborations with established partners; ② Scientific productivity and the R&D expenditure play a crucial role in countries generating dominant scientific relationships based on international scientific cooperation, which is also significant for countries who seek to form dominant relationships; ③ Geographical distance is still a major constraint on generating international scientific ties between two countries. Countries that share the same official language have a strong tendency to form new collaborations. This paper reveals the role of endogenous structural factors based on edge dependencies and considers their impact on dominant international scientific collaborations. We introduce GERGM to scientometrics, which has been applied to avoid information being lost in traditional binary network simulations.

Introduction

International research cooperation plays a crucial role in tackling many of the world's major problems, and it has emerged as a trend in the conduct of scientific research (Chen et al., 2019). Countries have, with the aim of occupying the central position at the frontier of global science and technology, actively participated in international research cooperation. The 14th Chinese Five-Year Plan has said it will implement a more open, inclusive and mutually beneficial international science and technology cooperation strategy and integrate more proactively into global innovation networks. It is therefore crucial to understand the mechanisms and generation of international research collaboration.

Papers that focus on scientific theories and fundamental innovations have been widely used to measure international research collaboration (Machacek, 2022). The leader of international research cooperation usually plays a determining role in the initiation and promotion of research projects (He et al., 2020). In co-authored papers, the first author is the primary writer and the corresponding author has made the most significant contribution to the paper's scientific quality and innovation. The corresponding or first author is therefore considered to be the leader in research collaboration. The leader's identification in international research collaborations however varies slightly in each field. Correspondent authors are generally considered as the leader in the natural sciences (Wang & Zhang, 2018), whereas in the humanities and social sciences, both the first and correspondent author can have this status (Bornmann & Haunschild, 2017).

International research collaboration is influenced by several variables. Geographical distance restricts international research cooperation (Vieira et al., 2022); Countries that share an official language find it easier to develop cooperation (Ferretti et al., 2022; Jiang et al., 2018; Tang et al., 2022); High levels of research productivity and R&D expenditure can stimulate international research cooperation (Tang et al., 2022). Meanwhile, although exogenous dynamics such as the nodal attributes of countries and national proximity mechanisms have

been widely examined, scholars have given less consideration to the role of endogenous dynamics in international research collaboration networks. Topological analysis has extended scholars' knowledge of complex networks, and studies have found significant differences between international research collaboration networks with random networks in structural characteristics, including path dependence and preferential attachment. This means that the formation of international research collaborations is influenced by pre-existing relationships that cause some local network configurations (Hou et al., 2021). Social network structural features were therefore recognized as one of the main drivers in the formation and development of international research collaboration networks (C. Zhang et al., 2018). In responding to this observation, only a small number of scholars have productively explored this phenomenon, and most have limited themselves to correlation analysis.

In existing studies, the leadership of the two parties are not taken into account when the generating mechanism of international research cooperation is discussed. And existing studies mostly ignore the interdependence and mutual influence of relationships in the international research cooperation. In being set at the default of mutual independence, current research focuses on the mechanisms of exogenous national proximity and the effects of national attributes on international research cooperation relationships. This study engages 235,746 papers published in the field of artificial intelligence from 2001-2020, and uses them to quantify the research leadership of international collaboration. It applies the generalized exponential random graph model to systematically analyze the endogenous and exogenous mechanisms of research leadership in international cooperation.

Research design

Cooperative networks' explanatory models

Gravity models are based on Newton's law of universal gravitation, which was originally widely applied in the field of spatial econometrics. This law states that the gravitational force between two entities depends on their masses and the distance between them. Gravity models have recently been introduced to the field of scientometrics (Avdeev, 2021), especially in the research of proximity mechanisms within collaborative networks (Jiang et al., 2018). However, the gravity model's assumptions imply that the side links in the network are inter-independent – as a result, it fails to consider the social network's inter-dependencies into account, and also does not incorporate the network's endogenous effects into its analysis.

In contrast to traditional econometric models, the Exponential Random Graph Model (ERGM) has been used to model network formation, and to simultaneously take into account the mechanisms of country attributes and social network structure features (Abramski et al., 2020). ERGMs are used to measure the generation of research relationships in international collaboration as a stochastic process, and have been applied to the field of scientometrics in recent years (C. Zhang et al., 2018). However, ERGM is used to simulate binary networks and is unable to estimate and model weighed networks (Y. Zhang et al., 2020). In taking this into account, JD Wilson optimizes the algorithm for implementing the Generalised Exponential Random Graph Model (GERGM) and launches an application based on the R language (Wilson et al., 2017). GERGM is an extension of ERGM, and it estimates and simulates directed and weighted social networks, and has a wider scope of application. It is currently mainly used in the field of economics (Abramski et al., 2020), but is rarely applied to scientometrics.

Data sources generalized exponential random graph models

The Exponential Random Graph Model (ERGM) is an essential metric for the statistical inference of networks. Assume Y is a directed n -vertex network (adjacency matrix), where n denotes the total number of nodes and m refers to the total number of directed edges in this network. The ERGM estimator for network Y is given by

$$P(Y, \theta) = \frac{\exp \{ \sum_H \theta_H h_H(Y) \}}{c(\theta)}$$

in which θ is a vector of coefficients; $c(\theta)$ is a normalisation parameter; $h_H(Y)$ is a statistical vector in the dominant network of international research collaboration; H represents the network attributes that influence the formation of network relationships; and θ_H is the attribute's coefficient.

In observation network Y , there are essentially two steps in the generation of GERGM's probability distribution. It starts by specifying the joint distribution of the structure, along with the dependencies of capture Y on the locally constrained network X . In comparison to Y , which has the same vertices as X , the X has edge weights that are bounded and continuous between 0 and 1. X 's probability density function follows:

$$f_X(X, \theta) = \frac{\exp[\theta' h(X)]}{\int_{[0,1]^m} \exp[\theta' h(T)] dT}$$

$\theta \in R^p$ is a vector of parameters; θ' is the transposed vector of θ ; h is the joint characteristics of Y in X (i.e., a statistic that captures the network structure and dependencies) .

Second, network X is transformed to support network Y with a parameterized monotonic non-decreasing transformation, Y_{ij} is defined as:

$$Y_{ij} = K^{-1}(X_{ij}, \beta_{ij})$$

β_{ij} is the transformation parameter that captures the marginal attributes of Y_{ij} . The GERGM is therefore estimated as follows:

$$f_Y(Y, \theta, B) = \frac{\exp[\theta' h(K(Y, B))]}{\int_{[0,1]^m} \exp[\theta' h(T)] dT} \prod_{ij} k_{ij}(Y_{ij}, \beta_{ij})$$

$K(Y, B)$ is the Monte Carlo transformation of the network from $(-\infty, +\infty)$ to $[0, 1]$,

$k_{ij}(Y, \beta) = \frac{dK(Y, \beta)}{dY_{ij}}$. $h(K(Y, B))$ is a statistical vector that relates to the network's

probability distribution, which is calculated on the basis of constrained network X to capture exogenous effects and endogenous structure.

The features of the generating mechanism in dominant scientific international cooperation

(1) Endogenous structural factors

Mutuality is a structural feature that measures the "feedback" phenomenon among social network participants (Y.T. Zhang & Zhou, 2022). The Reciprocal Index established by Garlaschelli and Loffredo (2004), is used to measure mutuality. He Chaocheng(He et al., 2020)

finds mutual cooperations are becoming a widespread trend in institutional cooperation networks. This paper basically examines mutuality in the research leadership of international collaboration.

(2) National attribution indicators

As a typical social network, the network of international research collaboration is characterized by "preferential attachment", which means organizations prefer to form relationships with others who share certain characteristics (Shih, 2020). On this basis, this paper proposes that country attributes may affect willingness to establish research partnerships with others. In addition, we classify the effect of country attributes into sender and receiver effect upon the dominant network of international scientific cooperation. The sender effect refers to the probability that a node with a certain attribute sends more ties in the social network, and the receiver effect refers to the probability that a node with a certain attribute receives more ties in the social network.

Levels of research productivity were found to be strongly associated with international research collaboration. Individual scientists will always favor a wider range of collaborators as this will help to achieve higher productivity. National research cooperation is an aggregation of individual scientists, and countries with high research productivity tend to be more favored by foreign scholars as this produces an advantage in international cooperation selection (Yang & Liu, 2022).

R&D expenditure is a critical factor in international research cooperation. In referring to the micro-levels, Hou & Lei (Hou et al., 2021) and Zhou P (Zhou et al., 2020) argue funding can help to promote the availability of international research collaborations. National-level research cooperation is the aggregation of individual actions, and numerous countries have significantly enhanced their research competencies by increasing the intensity of their R&D expenditure, which has in turn enlarged the scale of their international cooperation (Lathabai et al., 2022). This paper uses the level of research productivity and R&D expenditure as country-specific indicators to examine the sender and receiver effect in the research leadership of international cooperation.

(3) National proximity

The concept of proximity is derived from economic geography, which researchers consider to be one of the essential elements for international research cooperation (Jiang et al., 2018). Face-to-face communication can significantly improve scientists' productivity (Kwiek & Roszka, 2022) by helping them to build up mutual understanding and trust and minimizing the risk of miscommunication (Vieira et al., 2022). As a consequence, it is more efficient for scientists who live closer in geographic proximity to collaborate with each other, and this also enhances the probability collaborative relationships (Vieira et al., 2022). Sharing a common language reduces communication difficulties (between collaborators) and increases the efficiency of cooperation (Gui et al., 2019). This paper examines the mechanisms of geographical and language proximity in the research leadership in international collaboration.

Variable selection and model construction

This paper develops previous research by adding the following variables to the GERGM (see Table 1). 'Mutual' measures the tendency of country 'b' to establish a leadership with country 'a' when country 'a' leads country 'b'. This paper draws on studies by Sun Yutao (Sun & Zhang, 2021) and uses the number of published scientific and technical papers to measure national research productivity. It then uses the proportion of R&D expenditure to GDP to measure

national expenditure on scientific research. In addition, it inserts language (*edgecov_lan*), and geographical (*edgecov_dis*) proximity into the model.

Table 1. Selection of variables.

<i>Variables</i>	<i>Structure</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
<i>edges</i>	○→○	Indirect reflection of the density of cooperation-led networks; a benchmark tendency to form cooperative relationships
<i>mutual</i>	○←→○	The tendency for countries to interact with each other to establish cooperative leadership.
<i>ln_paper_sender</i>	●→○	The effects of a country's research productivity on its sending research leadership.
<i>ln_paper_receiver</i>	●←○	The effects of a country's research productivity on its receiving research leadership with others
<i>economy_group_sender</i>	●→○	The effects of R&D (as a share of GDP) on the country's sending research leadership.
<i>economy_group_receiver</i>	●←○	The effects of R&D (as a share of GDP) on the country's reception of research leadership.
<i>edgecov_lan</i>	○⇨○	The effects of language proximity on research leadership in international collaboration.
<i>edgecov_dis</i>	○⇨○	The impact of geographical distance on the research leadership of international cooperation.

Data sources and research dominance measure

Data sources

This paper presents a sample of published scientific papers in the field of artificial intelligence, and draws on data from the Web of Science core citation database. The search formulas "(WC="Computer Science, Artificial Intelligence") AND (PY=2001-2020)" were applied, and returned 235,746 items. Raw data on national research production and R&D expenditure were taken from the World Bank's public database, and data on language and geographical proximity were taken from the CEPII database (see Table 2).

Table 2. Data sources of variables

<i>Variable names</i>	<i>Variable descriptions</i>	<i>Data sources</i>
Research Productivity	Research productivity of individual countries is measured by the number of scientific papers published	Web of Science
R&D Expenditure	Measured by R&D share of GDP	The World Bank
Language Proximity	If two countries share the same official language, it is recorded as 1, and is otherwise recorded as 0	CEPII

Scientific dominance measure

In this paper, the area of artificial intelligence that is part of the natural sciences was chosen as the sample, and accordingly the countries of the corresponding authors were recognized as the leader in the paper. And the width of the edges indicates the strength of research leadership between countries. In any paper i , L_{abi} is 1 if country “a” leads country “b”. I_{ab} is obtained by cumulating a quantitative indicator of the research leadership of country “a” over country “b”. It is calculated as follows:

$$I_{ab} = \sum_{i=1}^{m_{ab}} I_{ab,i}$$

Where m_{ab} is the set of co-authored papers when “a” is the lead country and “b” is a participating country.

Figure 1. Leading network construction for international research collaboration.

Note: AU represents the author and CU is the country. For example, paper1 has three authors from three different countries. The first author is the corresponding author, and the research leadership of CU1 over CU2 and CU3 is 1.

Results analysis

The evolution of dominance in international research collaboration

Table 3 shows the distribution of the research leadership of international collaboration (top 20). There is a spatial clustering of research leadership, and North America, Europe and Asia Pacific account for an increasing proportion of research leadership in international cooperation; meanwhile, countries in South America and Africa rarely have many opportunities to lead international collaboration and often play a participatory role in international cooperation. In the period 2001-2010, the US was the global leader in scientific collaboration between 2001 and 2010 (scientifically dominant 2489 times), followed by China (scientifically dominant 2253 times). However, in the period 2011-2020, China overtook the US to account for the largest number of leading international scientific collaborations.

Table 3. Distribution of dominant research.

<i>2001-2010 Research Dominance (Top 20)</i>		<i>2011-2020 Research Dominance (Top 20)</i>	
<i>Countries</i>	<i>Research Dominance</i>	<i>Countries</i>	<i>Research Dominance</i>
USA	2,489	China	12,750
China	2,253	USA	3,651
UK	1,415	UK	2,548
Germany	1,015	Spain	2,208
Canada	938	France	1,414
Spain	887	Australia	1,350
France	841	Germany	1,320
Italy	741	Italy	1,314
Japan	608	Canada	1,192
Australia	585	India	1,140
South Korea	524	South Korea	1,080
Netherlands	458	Iran	950
Singapore	448	Singapore	943
Switzerland	366	Brazil	610
Belgium	355	Japan	609
Israel	250	Netherlands	592
Brazil	246	Pakistan	578
Austria	244	Malaysia	546
Greece	237	Turkey	538
India	231	Belgium	522

Figure 3 shows a chord diagram of the research leadership flow of international collaboration in the artificial intelligence field (top 20 countries). China and the U.S are the tightest partners and China is gradually taking a leader in cooperation with the U.S. In the 2001-10 period, China collaborated with the US on an aggregate of 228 occasions (118 China-led; 110 U.S-led). In the 2011-2020 period, China collaborated with the US on an aggregate of 1073 occasions (682 China-led; 391 U.S-led). International research partnerships under US-led tend to be diversified, and their exported collaborative streams are spread evenly across countries. In contrast, international research partnerships under Chinese-led are more clustered, and their exported collaborative streams are mainly focused on the U.S, UK, Australia and Canada. There are also few star-nodes in the research leadership of international cooperation. From 2011-2020, ten countries with the largest research leadership account for 66.1 percent of the total number of research leadership in international collaboration, which reiterates that a few countries monopolize the social capital of international collaboration.

Figure 2. A chord diagram - the research leadership flow of international collaboration in artificial intelligence.

Note: Individual countries' flow coarseness represents the size of each country's sending research leadership, with each country's direction of research leadership indicated by colored lines.

GERGM estimated results and discussions

This paper uses GERGM to simulate and estimate the research leadership in international collaboration (see Figure 4). The node positions represent the magnitude of the estimated parameters, and the colored bars represent the confidence intervals for the estimated parameters within the 95 percent range.

(1) mutual effect

The coefficient of mutual effect is significantly positive in both the 2001-2010 and 2011-2020 estimates, which indicates the mutual effect can promote the dominance of international scientific cooperation. Furthermore, the estimated coefficients of the mutual benefit effect in the period 2001-2010 are much higher than the other variables, which indicates the mutual effect was the key variable that influenced the formation of dominant relationships in international scientific collaboration in this period. In a mutual effect, countries with existing ties tend to strengthen their collaborative research relationships, and countries that are excluded from network communities have less access to collaborative opportunities. As a result, once a certain connection path is formed between countries, it will be reinforced by inertia and form a specific network structure, and this will cause the path dependency phenomenon in the dominant network of international research cooperation.

(2) National attribution indicators

The coefficient of \ln_paper_sender is significantly positive in both the 2001-2010 and 2011-2020 estimates, and this indicates that countries with high levels of scientific productivity are more likely to establish leading scientific cooperation relationships with other countries. The coefficient of $\ln_paper_receiver$ is also significantly positive in both the 2001-2010 and 2011-2020 estimates, which indicates that countries with high scientific productivity are more likely to receive the dominant relationship sent by other countries. Overall, countries with more scientific productivity are more likely to have opportunities to lead and participate in collaborations. In the period 2011-2020, the estimation of the sender and receiver effect for

scientific productivity is significantly higher than other variables, and scientific productivity therefore became a critical variable in the dominant relationship of international scientific cooperation.

The estimated coefficient of `economy_group_sender` is significantly positive in both 2001-2010 and 2011-2020, which indicates that countries with higher R&D expenditure have a stronger chance of sending a leading research partnership to other countries. The coefficient of `economy_group_receiver` is significantly positive in both the 2001-2010 and 2011-2020 estimates, which indicates countries with higher R&D expenditure will have more opportunity to receive leading relationships from other countries in research cooperation.

Estimates of research productivity and R&D expenditure suggest that countries with high research productivity and R&D expenditure will have more opportunities to lead and participate in research collaborations. Countries that have already recorded a considerable number of scientific achievements are strengthening their scientific capacity by improving collaboration in international research, and they will consequently be better-placed to compete in future international research collaborations. This produces a "Matthew effect" in the dominant network of international scientific cooperation – in other words, once a country achieves success in scientific development, this produces a cumulative advantage that means it will be more likely to achieve greater success and progress in the future.

(3) National proximity

The coefficient of `edg cov_lan` is significantly positive in both the 2001-2010 and 2011-2020 estimates, which indicates that countries with a shared official language have a stronger tendency to develop international scientific cooperation-led relationships. But language proximity has, when compared to other variables, a smaller effect on the promotion of dominant relationships in international scientific collaborations. This is possibly because English, as the world's common language, which scientists use to write and otherwise communicate, has become increasingly widely used in the academic community, which has in turn reduced the impact of miscommunications caused by the language barrier (Vieira et al., 2022). In the period from 2011-2020, the value of the `edg cov_dis` coefficient has reduced, which indicates that the impact of the barrier of geographical distance (on international scientific cooperation) has decreased. There is however a possible explanation for this – although geographical distance continues to impose inaccessibility problems, the development of communications technology (C. Zhang et al., 2018) has greatly improved the capacity of international scientific cooperation since 2011.

Figure 2. GERGM parameter estimation results.

Research conclusions

This paper quantified the scientific dominance of international collaboration by considering the corresponding author as the leader of collaboration. It also used a generalized exponential random graph model to discuss the formation of international scientific cooperation dominated network by referring to endogenous effects and exogenous mechanisms.

The number of research leadership in international collaborations shows a clear spatial clustering that is mainly focused on North America, Europe and the Asia Pacific. China and the U.S, as the two countries with the highest number of research leadership, also show the strongest cooperation in the period 2011-2020. In addition to definitively leading research international cooperation with the U.S, China also displaced the U.S by recording the highest number of research leadership in the field of artificial intelligence.

There is also a significant endogenous mechanism of international scientific cooperation dominance, which means that countries with established ties will form stable collaborative groups and produce path dependencies that will make the network of international scientific cooperation dominance self-reinforcing. Once a link is established between countries, it is reinforced by inertia along established paths, which is attributable to economies of scale, learning effects and the constraints of vested interests. In the first instance, choosing countries on the basis of pre-established ties does not only reduces collaboration costs but also improves communication between countries during the process of deepening cooperation, which increases the efficiency of scientific cooperation. But this ‘pre-selection’ may also omit more suitable ‘partner’ countries and in turn inadvertently prevent some emerging countries from being integrated into the construction of international research cooperation networks.

With regard to the exogenous mechanism of international research partnership dominance, both the sender and receiver effects of scientific productivity and R&D expenditure can contribute to the establishment of international scientific partnership dominance. Research productivity and R&D expenditure are the main causes of the power-law distribution phenomenon in the dominant network of international scientific cooperation. Countries with higher levels of scientific productivity and R&D expenditure will be given more opportunities to lead and participate in collaborations, which will further expand their levels of scientific productivity and R&D expenditure, and this will create a virtuous circle, in which a few countries become the “star” nodes in the dominant network of international scientific cooperation and control a large amount of social capital. A large number of countries will be excluded from the dominant networks of international scientific cooperation – as a result, they will lose access to the global research frontier and their scientific competitiveness will gradually be depleted. In addition, geographical distance remains a major constraint to international scientific partnership leadership, although here it should be remembered its effects are substantially qualified by the use of a common official language.

This paper makes a number of marginal contributions. In theoretical terms, it provides insight into the role of endogenous structural factors (based on edge dependencies) in the dominant relationship of international research cooperation, which will improve knowledge of the formation process of the dominant relationship of international research cooperation. In methodological terms, it introduces GERGM as a simulation model that can construct directed and weighted networks – this is important because it avoids the loss of information that occurs in traditional binary network simulations and expands the scientometrics toolbox.

However, this paper has several limitations. First, it only explores the dominant relationship between international research collaboration in the field of artificial intelligence. Future research should therefore expand the data sample and conduct a comparative analysis between different subject areas. Second, it only considers the corresponding author as the lead author in international research collaborations. Future research should therefore consider similarities and differences between the first and corresponding author in international research collaborations.

Acknowledgments

This study is partially supported by the National Natural Science Foundation of China (71974030). Wencan Tian is financially supported by the China Scholarship Council (202106060134).

References

- Abramski, K., Katenka, N., & Hutchison, M. (2020). *A Network-Based Analysis of International Refugee Migration Patterns Using GERGMs* (页 387–400). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-36683-4_32
- Avdeev, S. (2021). International collaboration in higher education research: A gravity model approach. *Scientometrics*, *126*(7), 5569–5588. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-021-04008-8>.
- Bornmann, L., & Haunschild, R. (2017). Does evaluative scientometrics lose its main focus on scientific quality by the new orientation towards societal impact? *Scientometrics*, *110*(2), 937–943. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-016-2200-2>
- Chen, K., Zhang, Y., & Fu, X. (2019). International research collaboration: An emerging domain of innovation studies? *Research Policy*, *48*(1), 149–168. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2018.08.005>
- Ferretti, M., Guerini, M., Panetti, E., & Parmentola, A. (2022). The partner next door? The effect of micro-geographical proximity on intra-cluster inter-organizational relationships. *Technovation*, *111*, 102390. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.technovation.2021.102390>
- Garlaschelli, D., & Loffredo, M. I. (2004). Patterns of link reciprocity in directed networks. *Physical Review Letters*, *93*(26 Pt 1), 268701. https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevLett.93.268701?access_num=10.1103/PhysRevLett.93.268701&link_type=DOI
- Gui, Q., Liu, C., & Du, D. (2019). Globalization of science and international scientific collaboration: A network perspective. *Geoforum*, *105*, 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoforum.2019.06.017>
- He, C., Wu, J., Wei, Z., & Liu, F. (2020). Research Dominance Between Institutions and Its Proximity Mechanism in Research Collaboration: A Case Study of China's Biomedical Field. *Journal of the China Society for Scientific and Technical Information*, *39*(2), 148–157.
- Hou, L., Pan, Y., & Zhu, J. J. H. (2021). Impact of scientific, economic, geopolitical, and cultural factors on international research collaboration. *Journal of Informetrics*, *15*(3), 101194. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joi.2021.101194>
- Jiang, L., Zhu, N., Yang, Z., Xu, S., & Jun, M. (2018). The relationships between distance factors and international collaborative research outcomes: A bibliometric examination. *Journal of Informetrics*, *12*(3), 618–630. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joi.2018.04.004>
- Kwiek, M., & Roszka, W. (2022). Are female scientists less inclined to publish alone? The gender solo research gap. *Scientometrics*, *127*(4), 1697–1735. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-022-04308-7>
- Lathabai, H. H., Nandy, A., & Singh, V. K. (2022). Institutional collaboration recommendation: An expertise-based framework using NLP and network analysis. *Expert Systems with Applications*, *209*, 118317. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eswa.2022.118317>
- Machacek, V. (2022). Globalization of scientific communication: Evidence from authors in academic journals by country of origin. *Research Evaluation*. <https://doi.org/10.1093/reseval/rvac033>
- Shih, Y.-A., Chang, B., & Chin, J. Y. (2020). Data-driven student homophily pattern analysis of online discussion in a social network learning environment. *Journal of Computers in Education*, *7*(3), 373–394. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40692-020-00160-x>
- Sun, Y., & Zhang, Y. (2021). Does Overseas Talent—Attracting Program increase the research output of Chinese universities? —A study by taking the chemistry discipline of the universities of the 《211 Project》. *Science Research Management*, *42*(10), 20–27.

- Tang, X., Li, X., & Ma, F. (2022). Internationalizing AI: Evolution and impact of distance factors. *Scientometrics*, *127*(1), 181–205. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-021-04207-3>
- Vieira, E. S., Cerdeira, J., & Teixeira, A. A. C. (2022). Which distance dimensions matter in international research collaboration? A cross-country analysis by scientific domain. *Journal of Informetrics*, *16*(2), 101259. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joi.2022.101259>
- Wang, J., & Zhang, L. (2018). Proximal advantage in knowledge diffusion: The time dimension. *Journal of Informetrics*, *12*(3), 858–867. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joi.2018.07.006>
- Wilson, J. D., Denny, M. J., Bhamidi, S., Cranmer, S. J., & Desmarais, B. A. (2017). Stochastic weighted graphs: Flexible model specification and simulation. *Social Networks*, *49*, 37–47. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.socnet.2016.11.002>
- Yang, J., & Liu, Z. (2022). The effect of citation behaviour on knowledge diffusion and intellectual structure. *Journal of Informetrics*, *16*(1), 101225. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joi.2021.101225>
- Zhang, C., Bu, Y., Ding, Y., & Xu, J. (2018). Understanding Scientific Collaboration: Homophily, Transitivity, and Preferential Attachment. *Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology*, *69*(1), 72–86. <https://doi.org/10.1002/asi.23916>
- Zhang, Y., Chen, R., & Ma, D. (2020). A Weighted and Directed Perspective of Global Stock Market Connectedness: A Variance Decomposition and GERGM Framework. *Sustainability*, *12*(11), Art. 11.
- Zhang, Y.-T., & Zhou, W.-X. (2022). Structural evolution of international crop trade networks. *Frontiers in Physics*, *10*, 926764. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fphy.2022.926764>
- Zhou, P., Cai, X., & Lyu, X. (2020). An in-depth analysis of government funding and international collaboration in scientific research. *Scientometrics*, *125*(2), 1331–1347. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-020-03595-2>